

Effect of Tins Mnemonic Strategies on Achievement in Concept Algebraic Words Problem Among Basic Education Students in Nasarawa State

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Abstract

This study investigated the Effect of Tins Mnemonic Strategies on Achievement in Concept Algebraic Words Problem Among Basic Education Students in Nasarawa State. The study was based on a quasi – experimental, non-equivalent pre-test, post-test and post- post-test, control group design. Two research questions were posed and two hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The subjects were all 1853 students (1012 males and 841 females). The sample used for the study consisted of 83 (46 Males and 37 Females) JSII students belonging to two intact classes, randomly assigned to experimental and control groups using multilevel sampling technique, their selection is purposeful in order to have data that have state representative. A stratified random sampling approach base on coeducation was used for students' selection. The instrument for data collection was Algebraic Word Problems Achievement Test. The reliability of AWPAT was found to be $r = 0.82$ using Split – Half Method. The data collected were analyzed and interpreted using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions and analysis of covariance to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that Tins Mnemonic strategy significantly affect achievement of algebraic word problems among basic education students in Nasarawa state. It was also recommended that Tins mnemonic strategies should be adopted as strategy in algebraic words problem instruction for better achievement of basic education students in Nasarawa State. The study concluded that Tins mnemonic strategies can be used as an intervention to improve the academic achievement of students in concept algebraic words problem.

Keywords: TINS Mnemonic, Achievement, Algebraic Word Problems and Students

Introduction

Mathematics is a subject that affects every aspects of human life at different levels. Mathematics is seen by society as the foundation of scientific technological knowledge that is important in social-economic development of a nation. It involves calculation, computation, solving of mathematical problems. Nneji and Alio (2017) stated that Mathematics uncovers hidden patterns that help us to understand the world around us. Now, much more than arithmetic and geometry, mathematics today is a different discipline that deals with data, measurements and observations from science, with inference, deduction, and proof; and with mathematical models of natural phenomena, of human behavior, and of social systems. It may also be defined as, the study of quantity, structure, space and change; it has historically developed, through the use of abstraction and logical reasoning, from counting, calculation, measurement, and the study of the shapes and motions of physical objects. Mathematic is a way to settle in the mind of children a habit of reasoning Malik (2017). Phonapichat, Wongwanich and Sujiva (2014), stated that the "functional" aspect of mathematics stems from its importance as the language of Science, Technology and Engineering, and its role in their development. This involvement is as old as mathematics itself and it can be argued that, without mathematics, there can be neither science, technology nor engineering.

More so, the National Policy on Education states that mathematics education aims at developing individuals who are able to think mathematically, who can apply mathematical knowledge effectively and responsibly in solving problems and making decisions (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014). One of the major challenges of mathematics in the school system is how to learn its concepts and effectively retrieve the learned concepts. For learning to take place, students must interact with mathematics ideas in active and constructive way. There is need for students to be

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proactively involved in their learning, they should not be seen as people with nothing to offer, people who just go to school to receive knowledge from teachers. Researchers such as Obi, Abugu and Ayogu (2015) observed that despite the practical utilization, scientific, technological and cultural values of mathematics, its teaching and learning is still characterized with lots of challenges. According to Adeniyi (2009), the cause of the widespread low level achievements of students in mathematics could largely be ascribed to mechanical and uninteresting teaching strategies mathematics teachers adopt which are lacking of understanding of the real meaning of mathematical concepts.

Learning is a process which should produce desired changes in the behaviour of students. Consequently, the learning situations utilized in the classroom are important for the understanding of the concept taught. Learning occurs when insight is gained, and when the processes are understood, in short when interaction has taken place between the teacher and the learner and between learners and their peers. Some teachers still believe that knowledge is transferred to their students but in reality students learn by doing and this is reinforced by the use of innovative teaching strategies. Abdulhamid, Abubakar and Tela (2017) expressed that teaching mathematics requires application of effective methods that bring active learning, but the absence of this makes the students not to participate actively in mathematics class. Algebra as one of the major branches of mathematics concerns itself with the study of the rules of operations, relations, constructions, and the concepts arising from them, including terms, polynomials, equations, and algebraic structures (Morris, 2009). Algebra according to Adeniyi and Ibrahim (2015) is an aspect of mathematics which involves the use of letter and numbers. These letters combine with figures bring a lot of confusion to the students more so, with the letters changing values or one letter replacing another letter at intervals. Although, algebra is considered as one of the most important aspect of school mathematics; it does not only play an important role in mathematics but function as a gatekeeper to future educational and employment opportunities (Silver, 2017). Algebra is a foundation and language system on which higher order mathematics, sciences, technology and engineering courses are built (Musen, 2010). Algebra being useful in other branches of mathematics, gives compact formulae or generalization to be used in all cases. Algebra has practical value in many of the trades and industries, provides an effective way for expressing complicated relations, inculcate the power of analysis, and is a good instrument for mental training. Kaplan, Fisher and Rogness (2009) stated that algebra often serves as a gate keeper to success in post-secondary education, and many career paths. However, its learning has remained a significant challenge to students all over the world; there are three fundamental understanding in learning algebra which can serve as impediment to mastering it by many students, the abstract reasoning, the language and the structure.

Again algebraic word processes contain applications to word problem involving basic arithmetic operations with algebraic symbols, word problems leading to simple linear equations, simultaneous linear equations, quadratic equation, and practical applications to word problems. In view of the significance of mathematics to the individual's daily life and the society at large, it is anticipated that the students' achievement in the subject should be well above average. However, the persistent poor achievement of students in mathematics has been a major concern for parents, mathematics educators and government who spend a lot of money in funding education but to no avail. Mashina and Timayi, (2015), blamed the curriculum and methods of teaching rather than student's lack of capacity to learn. The selection of teaching technique is not an easy task, this is because there is no single method that seems to work well for everyone and all situations. In addition, every teacher should identify appropriate methodology based on the nature of the subject matter and instruction to be given. Most teachers use irrelevant and ineffective methods of teaching which among other factors contribute to students' poor achievement in Mathematics. The need to find reliable ways of improving students' achievement and retention in mathematics is becoming an international issue. This is because the Conventional method of teaching mathematics is no longer effective (Bolaji, Kajuru & Timayi, 2015). Also as a result, the external mathematics examinations are made up of algebraic word problems in form of mensuration, trigonometry, compound interest, to mention a few which are to be translated into algebraic expressions or equations and solved. Students usually perform poorly in these areas and the NECO Chief Examiner reports (2018-2022) attributed the students' failure to poor grammatical expression, misinterpretation of questions, weakness in algebraic expression and word problems, among others. The chief examiner reports suggested that Students should try to read and understand the questions before answering them among others. For the candidates' weakness in algebraic expression and word problems, Kovarik (2012) posited that the inability of students to understand the vocabulary used

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in instructions and word problems are among the reasons. Kovarik explained further that although, students may excel in computation, their ability to apply their computational skills in algebra will be hindered if they do not understand the vocabulary used in instructions and in the word problems' tests.

Hence, knowing and understanding the language of an instruction is an important factor in relation to how successful the student would be, especially those involving word problems (Adams, 2013). The difficulty of these algebraic words may be a major part responsible for poor achievement in mathematics. Word problems are simply problems situated in a real life context (Verschaffel, Van Dooren, Greer, and Mukhopadhyay, 2010); it is this characteristic that differentiates them from other types of problems. This context requires students to read and understand in order to solve the problem while at the same time incorporate their mathematical understanding. As word problems are not given in a "plain" mathematical expression, they require complex steps to solve (i.e. reading, comprehending, transforming into mathematical expression, processing the mathematics, interpreting result to context given, and evaluating the result). Despite their real life context, the context of word problems is "situated" or encoded into syntax and expression, familiar to mathematics (Reed, 2009). The role of students in reading and comprehending the words in word problems thus are affected by this mathematically-situated context.

In addition, memory of factual information is essential for success in addressing inconsistencies in mathematics achievement, additional studies are needed to determine if mnemonic strategy instruction can be considered an evidence based practice in mathematics as well. There are a number of mathematical mnemonic strategies (TINS, SOLVE) that are being used by secondary teachers across United States of America. For example, the National Training Network has published curricula (e.g., Algebraic Thinking) that are being implemented across the U.S.A by districts and individual schools with the TINS and SOLVE mnemonic strategies as one of its major components.

Mnemonic means are often applied in mathematics instruction to help students remember steps or operations (Mastropieri & Scruggs, 2013). A number of mnemonics means have been used with students, TINS with an acronym to represent each step for learners to follow. Tins is a mnemonic strategy, representing Thought, Information, Number Sentence, and Solution Sentence. The process of Tins involves think about what you need to do to solve the problem and circle the key words, circle and write the information needed to solve this problem, write a number sentence to represent the problem, write a solution sentence that explains your answer. Tins mnemonic strategy is also taught in an explicit manner to students. Tins is a mnemonic means for secondary students to improve their mathematical mnemonic skills (Mastropieri & Scruggs, 2013). This is the method that quickly and effectively expose students to new mathematical information. Begin by presenting students with a clearly defined explanation of the concept you are teaching, working sequentially through the steps required to complete an equation. Facilitate discussion with the class by posing questions based on information the students have already learned and build on their prior knowledge. In a study, Akinsola and Odeyemi (2014) conducted their studies effects of mnemonic and prior knowledge instructional strategies on students' achievement in mathematics, that teachers should create mnemonics that link old and new information in the students' memory, assess their knowledge at the start of instruction through examples that bridge students prior knowledge with the new to ensure improved performance and make teaching and learning of mathematics students – centered. More so Maghy (2015) examined the effect of mnemonics on Students' Performance in Algebraic Word Problems in mathematics at high school level. The results showed a significant difference in performance in favours of the mnemonics group. Also, the mnemonics group were observed to have better achievement compared with their counterpart in the conventional group. In a related study Shafi (2016) determined the effect of Tins strategy on students' Academic Achievement in mathematics. Result from the study revealed that students taught mathematics using Tins strategy achieved more in mathematics content than students who were not and male students were not significantly better than their female counterparts in academic performance when they were taught Mathematics using Tins strategy.

Gender is a moderating variable whose influence was investigated in this study. The choice of this variable is due to the fact the issue of gender in mathematics is still unsettled. The influence of gender on students' achievement in Mathematics has remained a controversial and topical issue amongst educationist and psychologists. Freud (2011) suggested that the difference in Mathematics achievement of male and female anatomy has bearing and indeed account

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for the difference observed between the personalities of men and women. These qualities, prospects and relations are socially constructed and are learned through socialization processes. Gisela (2011) observed the influence of gender on achievement and observed that male and female students perform differently in various subjects' areas of education. The issue of gender and its influences on academic achievement in school subjects is yet to be fully resolved due to conflicting research findings from one school subjects to another. Falayojo (2013) asserted that, the differences in achievement exist between boys and girls at various stages of schooling and that it is the age of the student that is important and that determine the achievement and not gender. Johnson (2016) however, observed that at the secondary school level, girls could not measure with boys, because girls abandoned their study of mathematics before they enter the senior classes of secondary school. In addition, international literature suggests that females' students perform better than male students (Hydea & Mertz, 2009). Research in Australia indicate that gender differences in mathematics achievement are reducing and shifting (Forgasz, Leder, & Vale, 2010). Vale (2009) found that many studies between 2004 and 2009 in Australia showed no significant differences in achievement in mathematics between males and females students, though male were more likely to obtain higher mean score.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are to Determine;

1. Effect of achievement of students exposed to Algebraic words problem using Tins Mnemonic strategies and those taught using lecture method in Nasarawa State.
2. Effect of Tins mnemonic strategy on students' achievement by gender in concept algebraic words problem in Nasarawa State..

Research Questions

The following research questions guide the study.

1. What is the mean achievement scores of students exposed to Algebraic words problem using Tins Mnemonic strategies and those taught using lecture method in Nasarawa State?.
2. What is the mean achievement scores of male and female students exposed to Algebraic words problem using Tins Mnemonic strategies in Nasarawa State?.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 levels of significance.

1. There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of students exposed to Algebraic words problem using Tins Mnemonic strategies and those taught using lecture method in Nasarawa State?.
2. There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of male and female students exposed to Algebraic words problem using Tins Mnemonic strategies in Nasarawa State?.

Methodology

This study adopted Quasi- Experimental design of pretest post-test, post-post-test non-equivalent control group design. The population of the study consists of all the junior secondary school students' studying mathematics in Nasarawa state. The target population of the study comprised of all the JSII students in the public co-education schools that was made of 1853 (1012 male and 841 female) in the 2021-2022 academic Session. The sample for the study consisted of 83 JS II students from six junior secondary schools. The study adopted multi-stage random sampling technique. Out of the three senatorial zones in Nasarawa State, three local government were selected, namely; Akwanga, Lafia and Keffi local government areas.

Their selection was purposeful in order to have a data that have State representative. Using the ballot technique, two schools from each of the three selected local areas were used, co-educational schools were drawn from the list of schools in the area of study, the bases for the selection of the participating schools were: The schools must be co-educational, there must be qualified Mathematics teachers who have been in the schools for a minimum of 3 years, school location, willingness on the part of the schools to cooperate with the researcher, and the schools must be distant from each other to avoid interaction effects. In each school, one intact classes were randomly drawn and the number in each class was collected through physical presence of students'. Algebraic word problem achievement test

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(AWPAT) was an instrument developed by the researcher consisting of 50 objective test items using content on algebraic word problem concepts. This topic is derived from the national curriculum for junior secondary school Mathematics and it was selected because it features in (JSSII) Mathematics curriculum. It was used to determine the achievement of students in algebraic word problem concept in Mathematics. The AWPAT was a 50 item multiple choice objective test with four options lettered A-D. The instrument was structured according to level of the cognitive domain. The instrument upon validation was trial tested on 32 JS II students in order to establish the reliability coefficients of the instrument. The internal consistency of AWPAT was found to be 0.82. The data collected was analyzed and interpreted using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions. Analysis of covariance ANCOVA was used for testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean achievement scores of students exposed to Algebraic words problem using Tins Mnemonic strategies and those taught using lecture method in Nasarawa State?.

Table 1: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviation of Basic Education Students’ taught AWP in Experimental and Control Groups

S/N	Variable name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Tins	23.89	1.64	
2	Lecture Method	13.76	1.45	

(Field Study 2021-2022 academic session)

Table 1 showed that the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of students taught concept in algebraic words problem using Tins mnemonic strategy was (23.89, 1.64), while the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of their counterparts taught using Lecture method was (13.76, 1.45).

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of students exposed to Algebraic words problem using Tins Mnemonic strategies and those taught using lecture method in Nasarawa State?.

Table 2: ANCOVA Results on Basic Education Students’ Achievements Scores of Experimental and Control Groups

S/N	Variable name (Strategies)	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Tins	23.89	1.64	0.03 rejected
	Lecture	13.76	1.45	

Significant (S) at $p \leq 0.05$ Source: Field Study 2021-2022 academic session

In order to test whether there was a statistical significant mean difference between the strategies, ANCOVA was computed. Table 2 shows that p- value of 0.03 is less than the p – value of 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significance was rejected at 0.05 alpha level. The result implies that there was a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught concept in algebraic words problem using Tins mnemonic strategy and those taught using Lecture Method in Nasarawa State.

Research Question 2

What is the mean achievement scores of male and female students exposed to Algebraic words problem using Tins Mnemonic strategies in Nasarawa State?.

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Table 3: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviation of Basic Education Students’ taught AWP using TINS Mnemonic Strategy Based on Gender

S/N	Variable name (Gender)	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Male	24.18	1.47	
2	Female	23.52	1.69	

(Field Study 2021-2022 academic session)

Table 3: showed the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of students taught concept in algebraic words problem using Tins mnemonic strategy in terms of gender, male was (24.18, 1.47) and female was (23.52, 1.69).

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of male and female students exposed to Algebraic words problem using Tins Mnemonic strategies in Nasarawa State?.

Table 4: ANCOVA Results on Basic Education Students’ taught AWP using TINS mnemonic Strategy Based on Gender

S/N	Variable name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Male	24.18	1.47	0.23 accepted
2	Female	23.52	1.69	

Not Significant (NS) at $p \geq 0.05$. Source: Field Study 2021-2022 academic session

ANCOVA result in Table 4 revealed that there was no statistical significant mean difference between male and female students who were taught concept in algebraic words problem using Tins mnemonic strategy. Hypothesis was not rejected at 0.05 alpha level of significance because p-value is greater than 0.05 .

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study showed that mnemonics strategies improved JS students’ achievement in algebraic word problems than students’ that were taught using convention method, similarly, Tins mnemonic strategy enhanced students’ achievement in algebraic word problems than conventional method. The findings are in line with the findings of Siegel (2017) who found that students achieved better with Mnemonic mode of instruction. The findings of this study is also in agreement with the findings of Akinsola and Odeyemi (2014), since mnemonic strategy enhanced students’ achievement in mathematics, teachers should create mnemonics that link old and new information in the students’ memory. The findings are as well in line with the findings of Maghy (2015) who revealed that mnemonic strategy is more effective than the lecture method.

The findings also revealed that male and female students’ achieved similar using Tins mnemonic strategy, even though, the male students had higher mean score than the female students’ in the achievement test. The findings are in line with the studies of Shafi (2016), who revealed that students taught mathematics using Tins strategy achieved more in mathematics content than students who were not and male students were not significantly better than their female counterparts in academic performance when they were taught Mathematics using Tins strategy. and Forgasz, Leder and Vale (2010), that gender differences in mathematics are reducing. The findings of this study contradicted that of Johnson (2016), who observed that at the secondary level, girls could not measure with boys, because girls abandoned their study of mathematics before they entered the senior classes of secondary school. This implies that mnemonic strategy is a gender friendly strategy. Also the result revealed that gender was not a barrier in students’ achievement in mathematics when taught with Tins mnemonic strategy.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, Tins mnemonic strategy enhanced and improved Basic students' achievement in algebraic word problems than the Lecture method in Nasarawa state. Also, Tins mnemonics strategy is gender friendly that is both male and female benefit from it.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Mathematics teachers should be encouraged to include Tins mnemonic in their instructional strategies to effectively cater for the diverse abilities level of students within their classrooms.
2. Periodic and regular training through seminars, workshops, conference and in-service programmes should be organized for mathematics teachers to update their knowledge on current and innovative teaching strategies at secondary school level by state government.
3. Mathematics teachers should constantly look for current and innovative methods of teaching Mathematics that would be more effective.

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